

Influence of the Precursor Composition on the Resulting Absorber Properties and Defect Concentration in $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnSe}_4$ Absorbers

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Abstract

In this paper the influence of composition variations during the growth of $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnSe}_4$ (CZTSe) layers on defect concentrations and final absorber properties is analyzed. The samples are prepared from sputtered metallic and alloyed Zn/Cu-Sn/(Sn)/Zn precursors. The variation of sputtered Sn content facilitates different forms for the embedded Sn (Cu_3Sn , Cu_6Sn_5 , elemental Sn). The predominating formation reaction during the subsequent annealing is tuned by the ratio of the alloys and the overall chemical composition in the precursor. During the high temperature stage of CZTSe formation the layer undergoes an in-process composition shift (Sn content variation), after which the final absorber composition is reached. As all absorbers are reaching a comparable end composition, in this paper the influence of the different precursor compositions and corresponding reaction pathways on the resulting defects and optoelectronic properties of the absorbers are addressed. Spectroscopic investigations were used to extract the defect configuration of the absorbers. The results are complemented with device performance measurements. Preferable precursor compositions leading to lower defect concentration and improved photoluminescence quantum-yield is identified. The obtained Urbach energy and V_{OC} deficit are among the most promising results measured in our laboratories.

1. Introduction

The quaternary compound $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnSe}_4$ (CZTSe) is a suitable material for thin-film solar cell applications with low toxicity and earth-abundant elements in the absorber. With a S/Se mixture (CZTSSe) and/or Ge alloying (CZTGSSe) the band gap can be tuned in the range of 1.0 to 1.9 eV

^{[1]–[3]}, which makes it also interesting for multijunction applications. Although, several theoretical studies have shown the potential to reach competitive efficiencies^{[4]–[6]} suited for industrial commercial application of this technology, a significant breakthrough above 15 % efficiency could not be reached yet.^[7]

Research efforts have been made for understanding the reasons for the existing efficiency limitations^{[8]–[10]} and many approaches for improving the device performance were tested.^{[11]–[15]} This includes the most recent efforts to control the Sn oxidation states during layer formation, doping strategies and combined engineering of interface and defects.^{[10], [11]} It has been shown that, depending on the configuration of precursors and the layer at the beginning of the selenization, as well as the composition and the phase structure, an influence on the Sn oxidation states, i.e., +2 or +4, is present and resulting optoelectronic parameters can be affected.^[11] A proper understanding and control of these aspects is expected to lead to a reduced excess charge carrier recombination in the bulk and at the interfaces, which can help to improve the performance of kesterite based solar cell devices. Several studies in the past demonstrated the dependence of the final absorber composition on the predominant defect clusters and their concentration.^{[16]–[19]} Apart from only a few approaches in literature, the composition during the absorber formation and the final composition of the absorber used for solar cell preparation are similar or not distinguished explicitly. The composition regime for kesterite solar cells with good efficiency is limited to a rather narrow composition region.^[20] Therefore, there is not much room for composition variations resulting in the formation of different types and amounts of point defects and clusters without leaving the region for good efficiencies. Thus, testing the effect of different point defect types and clusters on the optoelectronic properties of the solar cells appears to be hampered by this limitation. Approaches for kesterite growth with different starting compositions, i.e., Cu-rich, Cu-poor, or Sn-rich, with ending compositions in a similar range, and which are suited for preparation of well working devices, were reported by Mousel et al.^[21] They are showing the possibility to change the layer composition during or after the growth process, which can help to bypass this limitation for the process design. However, the major disadvantage of these approaches seems to be the need of adding complex post treatment steps such as specific chemical etchings.

In this study we use our growth process which was reported to include a tunable in-process composition shift. The starting composition and the composition during the main CZTSe formation stage can be significantly different than the final absorber composition due to a vapor-based tunable Sn-incorporation/-loss during the reactive annealing step. The process was demonstrated to yield decent device efficiencies > 10 % for a broad precursor/absorber composition range.^{[22]–[25]} The composition shift (of the Cu/Sn ratio) takes place during the high temperature regime of the annealing process. Depending on the Sn content in the precursor, externally supplied Sn is incorporated (into samples with Sn-poor precursors), or excess Sn from the growing absorber layer evaporates (from samples with Sn-rich precursors), under identical annealing conditions. With this process, due to the abovementioned composition shift, we can produce absorbers with similar final compositions, however starting from precursors with significantly different compositions. This allows to investigate the influence of different starting compositions and formation pathways on the resulting absorbers while excluding noteworthy variations of the final absorber composition. A combined setup with spatially resolved multi-wavelength Raman and photoluminescence is used to extract defect related information from the absorbers, the results are complemented with conventional Current-Voltage (IV), external quantum efficiency (EQE) and energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX)/ X-ray fluorescence (XRF) measurements.

2. Experimental details

2.1 Sample preparation

The used substrates were provided from former Manz Solar, 3 mm soda lime glass with two 250 nm Molybdenum layers. The substrates were plasma etched for 4 minutes before sputtering the precursor in a deposition cluster tool (from Von-Ardenne GmbH). The added historic samples were produced on similar substrates (supplied from ZSW, Baden-Württemberg). The substrates from ZSW were plasma etched for 6 minutes before sputtering.^[26]

Precursors were prepared with a stack order of $Zn_a/Cu-Sn/Sn/Zn_b$ from DC-sputtering with sputtering durations of $Zn_a = 324$ s, $Cu-Sn = 1625$ s, $Sn = (0, 81, 162, 243, \text{ and } 324)$ s and $Zn_b = 44$ s in a Von-Ardenne cluster tool with sputtering rates of approximately $0.22 \mu\text{gs}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-2}$ for Zn, $0.10 \mu\text{gs}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-2}$ for Cu-Sn and $0.29 \mu\text{gs}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-2}$ for Sn, see details in previous publications.^{[22],[24]} The Cu-Sn target has a homogeneous alloyed mixture with approximately 64 at. % Cu and 36 at. % Sn, resulting in a predominant formation of Cu_3Sn in the as-grown precursor layers. The added historic sample series has the same precursor stack with Zn_a variations in the range of (274 to 440) s and Sn sputtering durations of (0, 162, 324, and 486) s. The sputtering rates were comparable, no significant deviations are expected. Samples with similar final compositions were included in the comparison, devices with significant deviations (especially in the Zn content) were not included (see Figure S1).

The annealing step is performed in a conventional Carbolite tube furnace holding a quartz-glass tube with a graphite sample box placed in the center of the hot zone. The tube is evacuated and filled with pump/purge cycles with nitrogen beforehand, the base pressure before setting the process pressure was 0.2 mbar. The graphite box contains the samples, a previously optimized amount of (210 ± 2) mg 5N Selenium pellets,^[27] and (10.0 ± 0.1) cm of 4N Sn-wire $((37.0 \pm 0.4)$ mg). The sample annealing is then performed in the semi-closed (“hand-tight” screws to tighten the lid) graphite box in a 10 mbar N_2 atmosphere, at 530 °C for a dwelling time of 20 minutes. The heating ramp is 10 °C/min, the cooling is done with no temperature control by switching off the furnace and opening the furnace lid. The process does not include any post-treatment steps, no etching is required, the solar cells are prepared from as-grown absorbers after the annealing process.

The main data set consists of 5 $Cu_2ZnSnSe_4$ (CZTSe) thin films synthesized using the abovementioned precursor variations (photos of the samples are shown in Figure S2). Details about the used precursors and expected compositions are presented in the Table 1. Additionally, 2 big samples (approximately $20 \times 20 \text{ mm}^2$) with similar precursors as the 1st and 2nd samples were included to assess the homogeneity of the samples on a larger scale.

An attempt of removing oxides after storage from the A703 to A728 sample set using a 2-minute ammonia bath was made, no change was observed in the accompanied PL measurements, therefore no further discussion on this procedure is included in the manuscript. A CdS buffer layer was deposited using a chemical bath with CdAc, Thiourea and NH_3 , at a temperature of 70 °C for 10 minutes. The TCO layers (75 nm i-ZnO and 500 nm Al:ZnO) were applied in the Von-Ardenne cluster tool using a RF plasma deposition. No AR coating was applied.

2.2 Characterization methods

The nominal precursor compositions are extracted from measured data and are cross-checked by measured sputtering rates. The rates are corrected slightly for a more accurate match, which is described elsewhere.^[22]

Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) analysis has been performed with a FEI Helios 600i, whose calibration is regularly cross-checked with samples previously measured at the University of Luxembourg. EDX spectra were measured with a voltage of 20.0 kV and 1.4 nA specimen current at 5000x magnification. Per sample a total of three randomly positioned measurements were taken to cover a larger area and minimize possible artefacts occurring from possible uniformity. Additionally, the chemical composition of the samples was probed by X-ray fluorescence (XRF) using Fischerscope XDV spectrometer, previously calibrated by reference samples measured by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP).

X-ray-diffraction measurements (XRD) were performed on precursors with a PANalytical X'Pert MPD using copper anode material (Empyrean Cu LFF HR (9430 033 7310x) DK409667) with 40.0 kV and 40.0 mA operation parameters together with a 15 mm incident beam mask and a water-cooled PIXcel1D detector. Compounds were identified using the ICDD database.

Raman scattering spectra have been measured using FHR640 and iHR320 monochromators from Horiba Jobin-Yvon coupled with CCD detectors. The first system is optimized for the UV-visible spectral range, while the second is for the NIR spectral range. The measurements were performed in backscattering configuration through probes designed in IREC. One He-Cd and two solid state lasers were used as excitation sources: 1) He-Cd gas laser, 442 nm, power density $\sim 100 \text{ W/cm}^2$; 2) solid state laser, 532 nm, power density $\sim 150 \text{ W/cm}^2$; 3) solid state laser, 785 nm, power density $\sim 120 \text{ W/cm}^2$.

The used excitation wavelengths are resonant with different secondary phases that can be formed during the synthesis of the $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnSe}_4$ kesterite absorber layer, allowing detection of comparatively small amounts of the secondary phases. The 442 nm laser allows to detect ZnSe phase^[28], 532 nm allows to detect SnSe_{2-x} and Cu_{2-x}Se phases^[29], 785 nm allows to detect SnSe_{2-x} and Sn_2Se_3 secondary phases.^[29] Moreover, 532 nm excitation wavelength showed to be quite sensitive to the changes in structural/compositional properties of kesterite phase, while 785 nm excitation wavelength, being closer to resonance with CZTSe compound, allows to estimate changes in the band gap of the material. The measurements were performed in 28 points per sample (for the small ones), and 168 for the big ones to detect possible inhomogeneities. All the spectra were corrected by imposing the main peak of monocrystalline Si to 520 cm^{-1} .

Photoluminescence (PL) spectra were measured using a Sol 1.7 spectrometer from B&W Tek coupled with the probe designed in IREC. The solid state laser (532 nm) was used as excitation source. The PL system was calibrated using the spectrum of a standard tungsten halogen lamp. Comparative PL measurements were performed at the University of Oldenburg using a 635 nm laser and a spectrometer system with an InGaAs detector array from LayTec.

Current-Voltage (I-V) characterization was done under standard test conditions with an AAA-class sun simulator (Photo Emission Tech Inc., USA). External-quantum-efficiency (EQE) data was measured at room temperature in the spectral range of 300 to 1400 nm with a Bentham TMc300 monochromator, Quartz-Halogen and Xenon lamps and a Stanford research systems SR830 DSP lock-in-amplifier. The material's band gap E_G was extracted from the $\text{EQE}^2(E)$ plot. Urbach energies E_U were obtained by a linear interpolation of the linear part below the band gap of $\ln(\text{EQE}(E))$ plots, as described in^{[30], [31]}.

3. Results and discussions

3.1 Composition analysis

The compositions of the sample series from the manuscript were determined by EDX as well as XRF. The EDX measured data set of all final absorbers covers a range of (40.57 ± 0.54) at. % of Cu, (33.07 ± 0.70) at. % of Zn and (26.36 ± 0.65) at. % of Sn. The XRF results match well with the EDX data and cover a range of (40.56 ± 0.36) at. % Cu, (33.07 ± 0.81) at. % Zn and (26.37 ± 0.88) at. % Sn respectively. The added historic data set covers a broader range of approximately $(39 - 46)$ at. % Cu, $(29 - 38)$ at. % Zn and $(21.8 - 27.5)$ at. % Sn. A summary of precursor and absorber compositions is given in Table 1. A graphic overview of sample compositions is also given in a ternary composition diagram in Figure S3. A graphic overview of the added historic sample compositions is depicted in Figure S1. As can be seen from both, the precursor compositions systematically cover a broad range in the starting composition (relatively Cu-rich to Cu-poor composition due to Sn content variations). However, after the described annealing procedure the final absorber composition usually reaches the same value region with comparable Cu/Sn ratios. No noteworthy trend on grain size and morphology was observed.

The above-mentioned composition shift predominantly occurs due to the loss of the SnSe_{2-x} content from the layer or by incorporation of the SnSe_{2-x} content during the high temperature annealing process. We note that in our annealing process, along with the precursor sample we use elemental Sn and Se in the graphite box (see experimental details). The amount of Sn and Se were kept same for annealing of all precursors. To show the loss or gain of the Sn-content from each sample with more details, we have compared the EDX and XRF measured Cu/Zn and Cu/Sn ratios for all the absorbers with the corresponding precursor. Figure S3 and 1 show that precursors without any additional Sn content (black dots) from this series show a strong composition shift from Cu-rich to Cu-poor due to Sn incorporation, whereas samples with higher Sn-content (orange dots) show significant Sn-loss, i.e., a composition shift from Cu-poor towards slightly less Cu-poor (the same applies for the historic sample set shown in Figure S1). We note that the amount of Zn and Cu is not expected to change at our annealing temperature (i.e., 530 °C).

Figure 1. Cu/Sn and Cu/Zn ratio for precursors and absorbers for samples grown with different Sn content in the precursor. Precursors without any addition Sn content (i.e., precursor with Cu/Sn ratio = 2.33) show a strong composition shift of the Cu/Sn ratio (2.33 to approx. 1.55). Precursors containing higher Sn-content (i.e., with Cu/Sn ratio = 1.31) show a Sn-loss with an increasing Cu/Sn ratio (1.31 to approx. 1.47). The grey symbols show the negligibly changed Cu/Zn ratios for precursors and absorbers.

To analyze the phase mixture in each precursor composition, XRD measurements were previously performed.^[22] To compare the relative variation of the amount of the main Sn-related phases (i.e., Cu_3Sn , Cu_6Sn_5 and elemental Sn) in each precursor, we plot the extracted intensities of the corresponding XRD peaks (extracted from already published XRD diffractograms^[22]). Figure 2 shows that the relatively Cu-rich reference, i.e., Cu/Sn ratio of 2.33, contains predominantly the Cu_3Sn alloy. With added amount of Sn, the amount of this alloy is reduced, and the intensity of the Cu_6Sn_5 peak increases and finally saturates. With further incorporation of elemental Sn (i.e., precursors with a Cu/Sn ratio below 1.68), the peak intensity of elemental Sn increases significantly with no noticeable changes in the intensity of Cu-Sn alloy peaks. This suggests that after the saturation of the Cu_6Sn_5 alloy peak, the excess amount of the Sn in the layer does not react further with the remaining Cu_3Sn but rather accumulates as non-alloyed elemental Sn, possibly due to diffusion limitation in the layer hampering further reactions. A possible variation in the kesterite formation reaction due to presence of different alloys in the precursor layer is discussed in our previous publications, indicating that the presence of higher Cu_6Sn_5 amounts in the precursor can lead to a reaction pathway predominantly via the ternary phase based route (i.e., $\text{Cu}_2\text{SnSe}_3 + \text{ZnSe}$), which in combination with small amounts of elemental Sn also can improve the composition stability in the absorber by reducing the losses of volatile SnSe_{2-x} phases.^{[22], [23]} A higher amount of the Cu-rich alloy (i.e., Cu_3Sn alloy) in the precursor can lead to higher amount of Cu_{2-x}Se phase, which can increase the fraction of binary based reaction pathway. For samples growing with a small composition shift, i.e., a Cu/Sn ratio of approximately 1.6 in the precursor

and final absorber, we may expect less restructuring and re-organization of the layer (e.g., secondary phases, composition gradient etc.) during the growth process.

Figure 2. Sn-related precursor phase signals extracted from XRD measurements for different additional Sn sputtering durations. With adding Sn to the precursor stack, the amounts of present alloy types and the ratios of the two main phases (bottom half of figure) change.

3.2 Evaluation of secondary phases

Raman spectra measured under 442 nm excitation are presented in Figure 3. Alongside the characteristic peaks of the CZTSe phase, the peak of ZnSe secondary phase at 250 cm⁻¹ (and 500 cm⁻¹ for the 2nd order) is occurring. ZnSe secondary phase is clearly found in all samples, with the highest signals present in the sample with a precursor Cu/Sn ratio of 1.95, followed by the samples from precursors with a Cu/Sn ratio of 2.33 and 1.31. As Raman is a surface sensitive method, these variations cannot directly be linked to the overall quantity of secondary phases in the layers and can be rather strongly determined by the distribution of ZnSe in the layers (surface or bulk). Samples with these precursor configurations/compositions (Cu/Sn = 1.31, 1.95 and 2.33) undergo stronger compositional shifts during the annealing (compare Figure 1), therefore more restructuring of the crystal layer can be expected as mentioned above. In contrast, the sample with a significantly smaller compositional shift shows the smallest ZnSe signal in the series, i.e., the sample with a precursor Cu/Sn ratio of 1.68. This sample corresponds to a maximized share of Cu₆Sn₅ alloy in the precursor (Figure 2), a minimized amount of secondary phase contribution during the kesterite formation can be presumed from that sample. Samples below this amount of additional Sn sputtering have a higher fraction of Cu₃Sn over Cu₆Sn₅, samples above this amount of additional Sn sputtering begin to exhibit larger amounts of non-alloyed elemental Sn with a similar Cu₆Sn₅/Cu₃Sn ratio. Nevertheless, this trend should be further verified with a larger dataset.

Figure 3. Left - Raman scattering spectra of CZTSe samples measured under 442 nm excitation wavelength. Right - Relative amount of (surface) ZnSe vs calculated Cu/Sn composition ratio in the precursors.

Additionally, the secondary phase is not equally distributed on the sample's surfaces. As observed on the big samples (see Figure S4), for the sample from the precursor with a Cu/Sn ratio of 2.33, only the borders of the substrate (about the last 2 mm, caused by the sputtering mask / sample holder, and generally excluded from the solar cell area by scribing) show a high concentration of ZnSe, while the used active area without these borders has a lower concentration or is ZnSe-free. The same pattern can be seen for most samples, where after excluding the border regions, the main solar cell area shows mainly low to medium Raman signals for ZnSe.

In the spectra measured under 532 nm excitation wavelength (Figure 4), the secondary phase CuSe (main Raman peak at 263 cm⁻¹ [32]) was observed in some of the samples (precursor Cu/Sn = 1.95 and precursor Cu/Sn = 1.31). However, the measured amount of this phase is insignificant. The corresponding peak intensity is very low, and not present in all the measured points. This finding is also observed in the large area samples (Figure S5).

Figure 4. Left - Raman scattering spectra of CZTSe samples measured under 532 nm excitation wavelength. Right - Relative amount of CuSe vs calculated Cu/Sn composition ratio in the precursors.

Figure 5. Raman scattering spectra of CZTSe samples measured under 785 nm excitation wavelength. Red dashed lines indicate the positions where the main peaks of different SnSe_{2-x} phases are expected.^{[33], [34]}

In the spectra measured under the 785 nm excitation wavelength no secondary phases have been detected (see Figure 5). This indicates, that even in very Sn-rich samples from precursors with low Cu/Sn ratios no traces of SnSe_{2-x} secondary phases remained at the absorber surface, which is in agreement with the preformed composition shift explained before.

3.3 Assessment of the changes in the CZTSe phase

As mentioned above, performing Raman spectroscopy with a 532 nm excitation wavelength enables us to observe changes in structural/compositional properties of the kesterite phase, while with 785 nm, since it is closer to the band gap energy, small changes in the band gap of the material causes measurable variation of relative intensity of LO peaks due to a close to resonant Raman response. Additionally, PL data provides information about the radiative recombination in the absorber. The maximum position of the PL band also indicates changes either in the material's band gap or in the position of the energy levels of the electronic states involved in this radiative recombination.

The spectral behavior in Raman measurements was reported previously to be capable of indicating relative concentration differences of predominant defect clusters.^{[16], [35]} This methodology was here used to estimate the impact of process parameters on relative defect concentrations. The investigated samples were grown with varied Sn amounts in the precursor, while keeping the amount of all other elements and the order of sputtered layers constant, which was previously shown to have an impact on the formation pathway of the kesterite absorber layer and on the resulting properties of the final solar cells.^{[22], [36], [37]} The Raman spectra are shown in Figure 6a. The extracted relative defect cluster concentrations are summarized in Figure 6b and c.

Figure 6. a) Raman scattering spectra of all CZTSe samples measured under 532 nm excitation wavelength with indication of the ranges used for the assessment of defect concentrations. b & c) Extracted relative amounts of [V_{Cu} + Zn_{Cu}] and [Zn_{Sn} + 2Zn_{Cu}] cluster defects versus Cu/Sn ratio from calculated precursor compositions.

The samples show typical Raman spectra of CZTSe kesterite type compound with small width of the peaks and without significant changes of this value, indicating a good crystalline quality and no significant inhomogeneities. This also indicates that no change in the disorder of Cu-Zn cations occurs either,^[38] which is the result of the same temperature profile during annealing for all samples. The main changes (see Figure 6a, spectral variance) are found in the relative intensity of the peaks in the range 160 - 180 cm^{-1} , associated to the point defects in Cu positions (V_{Cu} and/or Zn_{Cu} , or their cluster^[16]), and the peaks in the range 215 - 260 cm^{-1} , associated to Zn substitutions (Zn_{Sn} and/or $2Zn_{\text{Cu}}$, or their cluster^[16]). It is worth noticing that previous studies directly showed the correlation between the relative intensity of the Raman peaks in the above indicated spectral ranges with the corresponding defects.^[16,17] This was further applied in the present study.

In Figure 6b and c we can see a change of the relative integrated intensity of the peaks attributed to $[V_{\text{Cu}} + Zn_{\text{Cu}}]$ and $[Zn_{\text{Sn}} + 2Zn_{\text{Cu}}]$ cluster defects between the reference sample (precursor Cu/Sn = 2.33) and after adding a thin Sn layer (precursor Cu/Sn = 1.95, includes additional Sn sputtering of 81 s). In accordance with previous studies the observed changes in the relative integrated intensity of Raman peaks can be associated with decrease of the relative concentration of both defect clusters when adding the small amount of additional Sn. This initial change in the defect concentration may be the result of introducing the Cu_6Sn_5 alloy which is occurring when adding the elemental Sn on top of the as-sputtered Cu-Sn-alloy layer which is predominantly Cu_3Sn in the reference case. A change in reaction dynamics and alloy / phase contributions can be expected. When increasing the sputtering time for additional Sn layer further, hence decreasing the Cu/Sn composition ratio in the precursor, a different behavior happens: a gradual change of the relative integrated intensity of the peaks associated to $[V_{\text{Cu}} + Zn_{\text{Cu}}]$ and $[Zn_{\text{Sn}} + 2Zn_{\text{Cu}}]$ cluster defects can be observed (decrease and increase of the peaks, respectively), indicating a trend of higher amounts of defects for increased Sn amounts, with the highest number reached in the sample with a precursor Cu/Sn ratio of 1.31. The presented set of samples therefore allows for a tentative identification of an optimum of added Sn in terms of defect formations (i.e., Cu/Sn = 1.95 and only 81 s additional Sn sputtering).

The Raman measurement is complemented with PL measurements, a summary of PL spectra together with the extracted relative quantum yield (QY) and the position of the maximum is presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7. (a) Photoluminescence (PL) spectra of CZTSe samples measured under 532 nm excitation wavelength. (b) Maximum Position of PL and E_G vs Cu/Sn ratio from calculated precursor compositions. (c) Relative QY vs. Cu/Sn ratio from calculated precursor compositions and (d) relative QY versus Cu/Sn ratio measured in the absorber by XRF.

The non-monotonous changes discussed in the context of Figure 6 are also observed in the PL spectra analysis (Figure 7). When adding an additional thin Sn layer (i.e., + 81 s add. Sn sputtering, $\text{Cu/Sn}_{\text{Precursor}} = 1.95$), an increase of relative QY and a red shift of the PL maximum happens. However, when adding more Sn, the samples in this series show a change of behavior, and the relative QY is decreasing while the maximum shows a blue shift. The available historic data (included in Figure 7b for the reference with $\text{Cu/Sn} = 2.33$, and for samples with $\text{Cu/Sn} = 1.68$ and 1.31) is matching with the obtained results in this series. Nevertheless, there is a clear correlation between the precursor composition and the optoelectronic characteristics when an additional amount of Sn is added. In Figure 7d the relative PL QY is plotted as a function of the resulting absorber compositions. A similar but blurrier trend can be recognized, as absorbers with overlapping compositions show different QY, particularly around $\text{Cu/Sn} = 1.55 - 1.60$, indicating that the measured absorber composition is not the only reason for these effects. The same behavior

was also observed for the PL peak position and for the Raman spectra analysis for $[V_{Cu} + Zn_{Cu}]$ defects (see Figure S6 and S7). A clearer trend can be seen if only the precursor compositions are considered. We may presume that this indicates that in addition to the mentioned influence of the final absorber composition there appears to be an additional influence of the formation pathway on these properties, which can be linked to different precursor starting compositions. Considering Figure 7d, distinguishable levels of PL QY were measured for significantly overlapping compositions in the absorbers, a clearer separation is present in the precursor composition picture. Generally, one can expect, that the variations in the overall defect configuration and resulting optoelectronic characteristics could originate from the combination of the precursor (influencing the reaction pathway) as well as the final absorber composition (the Cu/Sn ratio), which is of course determined by the composition shift during annealing and also partially by the precursor composition. However, the characteristic variation trend plotted with the precursor composition shows a significantly stronger trend in this case.

Furthermore, the change of the energy of the PL band maximum is also correlated with the change of the relative intensity of Raman peaks in the range of $245 - 255 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra measured under 785 nm excitation (see Figure S8). The observed direct correlations allow to suggest that the change of the energy of the PL band maximum (Figure 7b) is due to the changed CZTSe band gap. A combined analysis of the Raman extracted defect concentrations and the obtained relative PL QY and position is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Relative PL QY (left) and energy of peak maximum (right) are color plotted on a defect concentration plot: relative integrated intensity of Raman peaks related to $[V_{Cu} + Zn_{Cu}]$ vs relative integrated intensity of Raman peaks related to $[Zn_{Sn} + 2Zn_{Cu}]$.

Figure 8 combines the results obtained from Raman and PL analysis. It is visible that the changes of cluster defects and the changes of relative PL QY and of the PL maximum are interconnected.

Thus, when the concentration of defects increases, the PL band maximum blue shifts and the relative QY decreases. The sample with a precursor Cu/Sn ratio of 1.95 was found to have the lowest defect concentration and the highest relative PL QY as well as a red-shifted PL maximum position below 1 eV.

The trend observed in defect cluster concentrations and PL results, did not show a direct correlation with the IV performance results in this sample series (possibly due to absorber aging effects), however, improved performances relative to the reference were observed in the historic data set for samples from precursors with a Cu/Sn ratio below 2.0. The samples with precursor Cu/Sn ratios between 2.33 and 1.31 showed efficiencies above 9 % (see representative IV and EQE in Figure S9). Notably, the overall sample series did not show a clear correlation between the relative ZnSe amounts at the absorber surface and the resulting device performance or relative PL QY. As reported in our previous studies^[39] a small amount of ZnSe seems to be not detrimental in these devices (see also Figure S4 and the discussion in the context of Figure S11).

On the other hand, the specific device characteristics such as Urbach energy E_U and V_{OC} deficit (Figure 9) which are known to be directly influenced by defects show a clear correlation with the $[V_{Cu} + Zn_{Cu}]$ and $[Zn_{Sn} + 2Zn_{Cu}]$ defect configuration, like the trend shown in Figure 6b and c, the samples corresponding to Cu/Sn ratios in the precursor of 1.95 and 1.68 show the lowest E_U and V_{OC} deficit.

Figure 9. (a) Urbach energy extracted from $\ln(EQE(E))$ over Cu/Sn ratio in the precursor. (b) V_{OC} deficit relative to the band gap E_G over Cu/Sn ratio in the precursor. Both show minima for the samples with Cu/Sn ratio in the range of 1.68 to 1.95.

To summarize this information together with results for the defect concentrations an overview is presented in Figure 10. The information from Figures 2, 6, 7, and 9 are considered. It can be concluded that precursors with higher Cu_6Sn_5 contents (Cu/Sn ratio between 2.0 and 1.6) exhibit decreased defect concentration, improved PL QY, decreased E_U and V_{OC} deficit. A Cu_3Sn alloy dominated precursor (sample from precursor with Cu/Sn = 2.33) or significant contributions of elemental Sn (sample from precursors close to Cu/Sn = 1.33) indicate to have relative negative effects on the abovementioned properties. Similar observations were made in the literature.^{[40]–[42]} These positive indications exist within a range of precursor composition, the extrema, deviating

significantly from this apparently optimized process, show comparably worse absorber and device properties.

Sample number	1	2	3	4	5
Calculated Precursor Cu/Sn	2,33	1,95	1,68	1,48	1,31
Cu ₃ Sn in the precursor	↑	●	↓	↓	↓
Cu ₆ Sn ₅ in the precursor	↓	●	↑	↑	↑
el. Sn in the precursor	↓	↓	↓	●	↑
Defects (Raman)	●	↓	↓	●	↑
Relative PL QY	●	↑	↑	●	↓
Maximum PL Position	●	↓	●	●	↑
Urbach energy E_U	↑	↓	↓	N/A	●
V_{OC} deficit	↑	↓	↓	N/A	↑

Measured Values:	
↑	High value
●	Medium value
↓	Low value
Suggested impact:	
	Good
	Bad

Figure 10. Color diagram of the relative presence of different complexes in the precursors (according to XRD analysis), of defect concentrations found from the Raman spectroscopy and properties related to the optoelectronic quality.

4. Conclusions

Several publications in the past have shown in-depth analysis of the influence of composition variations on the quality of CZTSe absorbers and resulting devices properties. Most of these properties appear to be strongly influenced by the final absorber composition. The results of these previous studies were used in the following years by many groups for tailoring their process for fabricating CZTSe absorbers in the preferred composition regime.

The here presented study takes a slightly different approach: the composition of the precursor was varied significantly in terms of Cu/Sn ratio of 1.31 to 2.33 while the absorber compositions all reached a narrow range of 1.55 ± 0.07 . This has an influence on the reaction pathway during the absorber formation, including different starting points for the reaction in terms of composition and alloy configuration in the starting precursor, and different amounts and directions of composition shift of the Cu/Sn ratio during the annealing process (incorporation or loss of Sn). By this approach we can study a set of absorbers and devices, which have a very similar composition, but which were grown to a large extend of the reaction time in different composition regimes. This allows to investigate the impact of the composition during the onset of kesterite growth additionally to the final composition in the absorber.

From previous studies which indicated the influence of absorber composition on the concentration of defect clusters, we have anticipated that the reaction pathway, in particular the starting precursor compositions and composition shift could have an impact on this parameter as well, even if a similar final absorber composition is reached. The analysis presented in the manuscript showed that based on the precursor composition / alloy mixture and final absorber composition, an influence on optoelectronic properties can be observed, similar trends are visible in defect concentration assessed by Raman spectroscopy, PL position and quantum yield, Urbach energy,

and V_{OC} deficit. The lowest relative defect concentrations ($[V_{Cu} + Zn_{Cu}]$ and $[Zn_{Sn} + 2Zn_{Cu}]$ clusters) were measured for the sample with a precursor Cu/Sn ratio of 1.95. This precursor contains an alloy mixture with a significant amount of Cu_6Sn_5 and a Cu_3Sn amount which still predominant but significantly reduced in comparison to the reference precursors. Its final Cu/Sn ratio in the absorber was approximately 1.60 ± 0.02 . This is in agreement with the precursor composition regime for reaching the best optoelectronic properties and device performance, which is Cu/Sn = 1.68 to 1.95. These findings could help to tailor new strategies for improving the efficiency of CZTSe solar cells not only by observation of the outcome in device parameters but also in terms of control possibilities of the resulting defect landscape.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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